

International Collaboration in Enhancing Educado: Prioritizing Requirements for an Educational Platform Supporting Waste Pickers in Brasília

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Abstract

This article aims to streamline the collection and prioritization of requirements for the ongoing development of the Educado app and website — a platform designed to provide training across various fields of knowledge while fostering social and economic inclusion. By offering accessible and relevant educational materials, Educado seeks to break the cycle of poverty and enhance the quality of life for waste pickers in Brasília. The research follows a qualitative, exploratory, and applied approach, integrating market analysis, the Mudge Matrix for requirement prioritization, and analysis of user feedback previously obtained. It builds on an analysis of the app's previous development cycle within the Egalitarian Emerged project, part of the ERASMUS program funded by European grants. The study encompasses user needs assessment, product improvement identification, and requirement refinement. As a result, 144 structured requirements were defined for implementation in collaboration with students from Aalborg University (Denmark) and the University of Brasília (Brazil). The findings emphasize the significance of structured requirements elicitation and effective prioritization to ensure that software development aligns efficiently with user needs.

Keywords: Egalitarian Project; International Student Collaboration; Requirements Gathering; Requirement Prioritization; Waste Pickers.

1 Introduction

As part of the Egalitarian portfolio, an Erasmus+ program funded by European grants, Educado was designed to promote education and digital inclusion to waste pickers in Brasília. It aims to provide personalized content based on the knowledge needs of users with little access to education. Given the social relevance of the solution, ensuring that the digital platform effectively meets user needs requires a new software requirements list for the developers to work with.

Since 2018, the app (software designed for users) and website (designed for content creators) have been prototyped, developed, and improved. Throughout the Educado concept, different development cycles were implemented, each with distinct strategies and outputs. These phases contributed to the platform's evolution and generated documentation that now serves as the basis for the current study (Melo, 2024).

However, how can users' needs be identified, prioritized, and implemented consistently and efficiently? The present study aims to structure and prioritize the requirements for the continued enhancement of the Educado application and website.

Insights into user needs were documented in earlier phases of the project through exploratory initiatives and stakeholder interactions. These prior findings are consolidated to support the current refinement of requirements (Nunes et al., 2023).

Market research is also necessary to explore new potential features. It is characterized by a divergent focus on uncovering previously unrecognized possibilities and a convergent focus on reaching conclusions based on previously raised hypotheses (Ferreira, 2023). Lastly, these requirements must be ranked and prioritized according to their importance and impact on future development.

The following sections present the research stages, including the methodologies applied, proposed solutions, and recommendations for future work.

2 Theoretical Reference

This section aims to map the literature on the topic, which will be divided into two subtopics.

2.1 Usability Testing

As La Bara et al. (2021) mention, "A broader definition of usability may include the user's experience of the quality of the product or system."

Therefore, usability can also be understood as "The ease of using and learning about these applications and websites is related to the concept of usability, thus generating software with a higher level of quality" (De Camargo, 2021).

In this context, it is also necessary to understand the concept of usability testing, which, in the words of Barboza (2023), is "a method of verifying the functionalities of the interface of a digital platform. It is used on websites, applications, and other tools, leading real users to perform certain tasks."

It should also be noted that the usability test must explain the reason for each planned activity and highlight how adding a new function can help execute the proposed tasks (Oliveira, 2021).

2.2 Requirements Gathering

After carrying out usability tests by the collectors, it is necessary to define the methodology for gathering requirements to be developed by the developers of the AAU Software Five discipline, based on the identification of usability testing needs. Silva (2023) states, "Requirements gathering is the process of identifying, documenting, and verifying users' needs and expectations for a software system. It involves collecting relevant information to understand the context, desired functionalities, and constraints that must be considered during software development."

In this context, the most frequently used methodologies for requirements gathering are interviews, surveys and questionnaires, meetings and scenarios, focus groups, brainstorming, and JAD/RAD (Siqueira, 2023). Analyzing each method is essential for selecting the most coherent research field.

In the words of Siqueira (2023), "Interviews are the most used elicitation techniques, commonly used in any development as they represent one of the most natural forms of communication between people". Questionnaires "are used in various scientific areas, such as opinion polls, censuses, and other research types". However, it is crucial to design questionnaires carefully to ensure that questions are clear and relevant to the research objectives.

Brainstorming is one of the oldest and most well-known group meeting techniques for generating ideas. In the context of requirements gathering, brainstorming allows each person to inspire the other to create ideas that can contribute to solving the problem, whether in one or several meetings.

Regarding JAD (Joint Application Design), according to Siqueira (2023), "It was developed by IBM to accelerate the development of information systems and is based on group dynamics accompanied by planning, structuring, and systematization of meetings."

Finally, the methodology used to gather requirements was based on two stages of work: the analysis of usability tests and market research. The usability tests were carried out at the beginning of the year, and the latest tests served as input to gather the requirements for the app and website's functioning and improvement. Furthermore, other features could be identified during market research with different platforms.

2.3 Mudge Diagram

The Requirements Prioritization Matrix, also known as the Mudge Diagram, is a tool for systematically ranking requirements based on their relative importance. The model was initially used in Value Engineering and has since been widely adapted for prioritizing requirements in engineering projects and product development (Camolesi, 2020).

This approach relies on pairwise comparisons between requirements: each pair is evaluated by relevance, with weights assigned using an ordinal scale. After all comparisons, the values are summed to rank requirements by priority, from highest to lowest. This technique facilitates decision-making in projects with limited resources, ensuring that efforts are focused on the most impactful requirements (Souza et al., 2021).

In addition to being simple to apply, the Mudge Diagram is effective in collaborative contexts and can be adapted for different types of evaluations, including those involving multiple evaluators or weighted criteria. In product engineering projects, such as medical tools or educational software development, it has proven valuable in guiding the design phase based on structured data.

3 Methodology

This section presents the methodology used during the research. In it, the applied method and its structure will be explained.

3.1 Research Method

The methodology used was applied in nature, with an exploratory objective and a qualitative approach. The case study of the Educado project was used as a research strategy. Applied research "refers to research designed to develop new knowledge for practical purposes" (Pereira, 2020). This way, the study's nature is applied as it addresses a real problem facing collectors.

The research aims to deepen the understanding of the problem and expand knowledge on the topic, so it falls into the exploratory case study category. The approach is classified as qualitative, which attempts to understand better why things are the way they are in the social world and why people act the way they do. Ernest et al. (2023).

3.2 Research Structure

The research structure was composed of 5 stages, exemplified by Figure 1.

Figure 1. Study methodological steps.

The first stage of this research evaluates the progress of software development up to the current stage based on the proposal. Based on this assessment, the work will be consolidated and adequately documented, providing a structured basis for the subsequent stages of the research. Furthermore, a backlog was created to guide future activities.

Subsequent steps should involve proposing new solutions based on comparative analyses of other software available on the market. This helps understand the strengths and weaknesses of the Educado system compared to similar systems.

Based on these analyses, the outputs were formalized by defining functional and non-functional requirements. These requirements were identified and refined using results from previously conducted usability tests. Although new usability tests were not performed during this project, the insights from earlier evaluations were used to inform the requirement prioritization process. After determining the requirements, the list was reviewed and organized for formal delivery.

4 Results and Discussions

This section presents the requirements identified based on the results of usability tests carried out in earlier stages of the project, which were used as input for this study. It also includes the outcomes of the last development cycle, a comparative analysis, and the requirements prioritization process, culminating in the final list of requirements to be developed by students at Aalborg University in the upcoming semester.

4.1 Comparative Analysis

The first stage consisted of synthesizing the development of the 2023 Educado version, represented by Figure 2. It involved analysing screens already developed for the website and the mobile app and evaluating developer performance from the previous development cycle. These elements were transformed into a formal report to guide the following phases of the project.

Figure 2. 2023 Version of the Educado Website and App.

Drawing from consolidated documentation, the comparative analysis provided an overview of the project, helping identify outdated requirements and opportunities for new functionalities, structured through a SWOT matrix and benchmarking. The matrix was conducted to assess the Educado platform's strategic position and define future enhancements, offering a perspective on internal capabilities and external challenges (Yadav & Sharma, 2020). The identified topics were:

- **Strengths:** Has a certificate from the University of Brasília, a renowned institution; international recognition through partnership with Aalborg University; offers free courses.
- **Weaknesses:** Decentralization of work; lack of "know-how" from students to use the app; communication difficulties with developers (different languages and countries).
- **Opportunities:** Focus on a specific niche (waste pickers); few competitors in the same niche; received investment from the Egalitarian project and UnB for development.
- **Threats:** Lack of attention to LGPD requirements; difficulty of use by illiterate users; possible breaches of the user data storage system.

Based on a benchmarking analysis, new features were identified to enhance the platform's experience. For the mobile app, improvements include a general ranking system, post-exercise feedback, access to downloadable materials, a centralized progress area, social media integration, completion certificates, and weekly performance reports. On the website, navigation guides, student-view simulation, multi-instructor courses, and weekly performance tracking were introduced. This comparative study highlighted usability best practices and supported mapping features aligned with market-leading solutions.

4.2 Gathering Requirements

The detailed survey introduces functional and non-functional requirements for the Educado app and website systems. It aims to identify the project status while providing an overview of the functionalities and their classifications in terms of progress. 144 (one hundred and forty-four) requirements were raised.

The requirements were classified into five distinct status categories to enhance the efficiency of management and monitoring of progress, which we can mention: new - newly identified requirements that have not yet been worked on; improvement - existing requirements that require usability improvement; error - requirements related to defects or bugs that need to be corrected; untested - requirements implemented, but have not yet undergone validation testing; done - requirements implemented and validated.

Figure 2 presents the status distribution of the 62 website requirements, revealing that the majority (45%) remain in the not tested category. The 27% of new requirements reflect the ongoing project. Improvements

and bugs each account for 10% and 8%, respectively, emphasizing the iterative refinement process. Meanwhile, only 8% of the requirements have reached the done status.

Figure 2. Distribution of Web Requirements by Status in the Educado Project.

In contrast, Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of the 82 app requirements. The new category holds 35% of the requirements, representing an evolution in functionalities for the end users. 24% are improvements, while 11% are bugs, indicating a need to refine the current app. Only 14% of the requirements are completed in the done category, and 16% are not tested.

Figure 3. Distribution of App Requirements by Status in the Educado Project.

This analysis provides a development overview of each platform and supports the development prioritization presented in the next section.

4.3 Requirements Prioritization

Requirements prioritization can be used to select which customer requirements will or will not be included in the product. The software establishes relative preferences or needs among requirements and defines a sequential order.

For this research, the requirements prioritization methodology used was the Pairwise Comparison Matrix, also known as the Mudge Diagram. This method allows the comparison, in pairs, of a set of customer requirements to determine the relative importance of each one (Nogueira, 2023). In that case, the requirements are catalogued as letters (A, B, C...n), and a table is created comparing each requirement and assigning its importance value from 0 (equal importance) to 5 (critical importance).

Therefore, the Educado requirements were prioritized through six Mudge Diagrams: three for the app system and three for the website. Each set of diagrams categorizes requirements into three groups: new requirements, improvement requirements, and error-related requirements, comparing items within the same category. In

order to illustrate this process, Table 1 presents the updated list of error-related requirements for the app, each with a clear identifier for use in the corresponding diagram.

Table 1. Error-related requirements list catalogued for the Educado app.

ID	Requirements
A	As a waste picker, I would like to click on the button to register and go to registration page
B	As a waste-picker, I want to have the ability to register as a new user, so that I can log in to the application going forward
C	As a waste picker, I want to learn more about the course before subscribing, so that I can choose better
D	As a waste picker, I want to be able to review the exercises and get feedback from it
E	As a waste picker, I want to be able to finish de exercise
F	As a waste picker, I want to see me getting points after completing exercises on a course
G	As a waste picker, I want to see all the courses that I did download when I am offline
H	As a waste picker, I want to upload a new profile picture or choose the default profile picture in my profile settings
I	As a waste picker, I want to be able to see and edit relevant data about my profile on the profile page.

Subsequently, the Mudge Diagram was built as presented in Table 2, which prioritizes the app error-related requirements. This structured visualization offers a systematic comparison that resulted in absolute and relative scores, indicating the frequency and impact of each requirement within the dataset. Higher scores indicate more critical requirements or are frequently associated with multiple errors, necessitating prioritization in the debugging and refinement process.

Table 2. Mudge Diagram of error-related requirements for the Educado app.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9		
ID	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	Absolute Score	Relative Score
A	A	A1	A3	D2	0	0	A3	A1	A1	9	13,85%
B		B	B3	0	E3	0	B1	0	I1	6	9,23%
C			C	D3	E5	F3	G2	H1	I3	0	0,00%
D				D	E3	D1	D3	D1	I1	10	15,38%
E					E	E3	E3	0	E1	24	36,92%
F						F	F1	F1	I1	5	7,69%
G							G	0	I1	2	3,08%
H								H	I1	1	1,54%
I									I	8	12,31%

The other constructed Mudge Diagrams follow the same structure pattern that will guide the development team with a data-driven approach. This method ensures the software resolution is aligned with project goals and the user's needs while first addressing the most impactful issues to optimize system functionality. Following this, an organized list of requirements was created for developers from the Software Five discipline at AAU to work in the second semester of 2024. The following section will detail these requirements.

4.4 List of Requirements to be Developed

Drawing upon the Mudge Diagram method, the requirements were organized in descending order of priority, with their ranking classification, corresponding letter for identification, and description. These are described as

user stories, an agile methodology technique to make the system's functionalities straightforward from the end user's point of view, facilitating the team's understanding (Domínguez et al., 2024). Table 3 presents the result of the app error-related requirements with that layout.

Table 3. Prioritized list of error-related requirements for the Educado app.

Priority	ID	Requirements
1	E	As a waste picker, I want to be able to finish the exercise
2	D	As a waste picker, I want to be able to review exercises and receive <i>feedback</i> from them
3	A	As a waste picker, I would like to click the button to register and go to the registration page
4	I	As a waste picker, I want to see and edit relevant data about my profile on the profile page
5	B	As a waste picker, I want to be able to register as a new user so that I can <i>log</i> in to the app going forward
6	F	As a waste picker, I want to see my points being scored after completing exercises in a course
7	G	As a waste picker, I want to see all the courses I have downloaded when I am offline
8	H	As a waste picker, I want to upload a new profile photo or choose the default photo in my settings
9	C	As a waste picker, I want to know more about the course before signing up so I can choose better

Replicating the established pattern illustrated in Table 3, additional prioritized lists were created for the remaining requirement categories. The six sets (new and improvement-related requirements for the app and error-related, new, and improvement requirements for the website) reflect the categorization and quantity of requirements identified in Section 4.1. This means that the method was consistently applied to all 144 requirements.

Therefore, the final list contains the expected outcome of further software implementation, ensuring incremental value delivery aligned with user needs.

Based on the competitive analyses and document consolidation, the outputs could be formalized by defining functional and non-functional requirements. These requirements were validated and prioritized according to the research's needs and objectives. After determining the requirements, the list was reviewed and refined to prepare it for formal delivery.

5 Conclusion

Consolidating the gathering and prioritization of app and website requirements for Educado, an extension project with international cooperation, is relevant to the discipline of Software Five from Aalborg University (AAU), which is responsible for software development. Students aim to deliver incremental value to users through agile methodology, Scrum, using the problem-based learning methodology (PBL), which will scope the requirements defined in this work.

The project aimed to identify, prioritize, and implement improvements to the Educado app and website to improve the user experience. In this way, it was possible to carry out a comparative analysis of the screens already developed throughout the project and a market analysis to identify outdated requirements and opportunities for new functionalities. It was also possible to classify the requirements into five status categories to subsequently prioritize them. Finally, as the last result of the research, the team summarized the list of requirements to be developed next. Thus, the objective of the work was completed.

Due to communication issues with the previous semester's developers, the workshop to understand their perception of the format, beyond the collected data, could not be held. Additionally, status requirement updates were delayed as the other team was still testing the application and website. These challenges highlight opportunities for future work on improving user-developer communication through requirements.

However, the research results were successfully achieved, with requirements raised, categorized, and prioritized into transparent and objective lists. This work provides a solid foundation for the Educado project and its software development cycle in the second half of 2024 in partnership with Aalborg University (AAU) developers. Therefore, it is ensured that future implementations are aligned with users' needs and expectations, with a solid basis for usability tests at the University of Brasília, followed by the development.

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